

ANALYSIS OF FLAVONOID COMPOSITION OF *ALLIUM MOTOR* BY HPLC**Yuldoshev S.S.**

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Relevance: In recent years, the isolation of bioactive compounds from natural sources and the evaluation of their pharmaceutical potential have become important directions of scientific research. In particular, plants of the genus *Allium* have long been used in traditional medicine. Their chemical composition has been shown to include flavonoids, phenolic acids, vitamins, and other biologically active compounds. In this context, a comprehensive chemical analysis of *Allium motor* and the assessment of its pharmaceutical and bioactive properties represent a relevant task.

Aim of the study. The main aim of this study was to identify flavonoids present in the extracts of vegetative parts of *Allium motor* using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), to determine their quantitative proportions, and to substantiate their pharmaceutical significance.

Methods. As research objects, ethanol extracts were prepared from the leaves and bulbs of *Allium motor*. Analytical tests were carried out using an Agilent HPLC system operating with ChemStation software. A diode array detector (DAD) was used at wavelengths of 254 nm, 265 nm, and 281 nm. Standard reference substances such as apigenin, rutin, and resveratrol were applied for comparison.

Results. HPLC analysis confirmed the presence of several flavonoid compounds in *Allium motor* extracts. Their relative contents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Relative content of flavonoids in *Allium motor* extract (based on HPLC results)

No	Compound	Retention time (min)	Relative content (%)
1	Apigenin	1.71–1.73	18.3 – 24.0
2	Rabinin	1.93–1.94	4.6 – 40.9
3	Rutin	2.35	3.7 – 3.9
4	Resveratrol	7.13	3.7 – 22.3
5	Other flavonoids	1.62–1.81	16.4 – 46.8

The results indicate that *Allium motor* is rich in flavonoids. Rabinin and apigenin were identified as the main components, while resveratrol and rutin also made up a significant proportion of the composition. The diversity of flavonoids demonstrates the strong antioxidant potential of the plant. Furthermore, the high content of rabinin suggests possible immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory properties. The considerable presence of apigenin supports its sedative and antiallergic activity. The detection of resveratrol indicates potential cardioprotective and anticancer effects. Compared to data on other *Allium* species reported in the literature, *Allium motor* appears to be distinguished by its richness in bioactive compounds. Thus, extracts of this plant may represent a promising source for the development of new phytopharmaceuticals.

Conclusions. *Allium motor* is rich in flavonoids, with rabinin, apigenin, rutin, and resveratrol being the main components. The chemical composition of the plant confirms its antioxidant and pharmaceutical potential. The findings provide a scientific basis for the development of new phytopreparations and their use in clinical pharmacy.